

Abstract

Estimation of depth in two-dimensional images is among the challenging topics in Computer Vision. This is a well-studied but also an ill-posed problem, which has long been the focus of intense research. This paper is an in-depth review of the topic, presenting two aspects, one that considers the mechanisms of human depth perception, and another that includes the various Deep Learning approaches. The methods are presented in a compact and structured way that outlines the topic and categorizes the approaches according to the line of research followed in the recent decade. Although there has been significant advancement in the topic, it was without any connection with human depth perception and the potential benefits from this sector.